

SECTION OF BIOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

MICROORGANISMS IN SOILS OF LEGUMINOUS PLANTS OF THE ABSHERON PENINSULA

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Abstract

The article deals with the types of microbes finding in Absheron soils, their functions of microorganisms in the soil, and the influence of the environment on their livelihoods. On the dynamics of the number of microorganisms in the soil influence not only humidity and temperature, but also the phase of plant development, the entry of organic decay into the soil, the accumulation of microbial metabolites and much more. In addition to seasonal fluctuations in numbers microorganisms, changes in the number and structure of microbial groups are observed in the soil over short periods of time - months, weeks, and even day.

Keywords: Microorganisms, soil, fertility.

Soil bacteria trace their history from when representatives of organic life only to those times - started to get out on land. Soil is a complex substrate. Pinpoint the factors that regulate microbiological processes it is extremely difficult. However, the heterogeneity of the soil leads to the fact that for organisms of different species, it acts as a different Wednesday. For example, in fertile soil, the total biomass bacteria reaches 500 kg/ha or more, microorganisms are of the greatest importance for soil fertility, involved in the nitrogen cycle in nature: nitrogen-fixing bacteria of the genera *Azotobacter*, *Rhizobium*, actinomycetes of the genus *Frankia* and others; nitrifying bacteria; spore-forming rods of the genera *Bacillus* and *Clostridium*. All living inhabitants of the soil can be attributed to three super-kingdoms (non-nuclear - Acaryotae; pre-nuclear -Procaryotae; nuclear - Eucaryota) Soil bacteria form three main classes: Actinomycetae, Eubacteriae and Myxobacteriae, which include microorganisms of various shapes and functions. The main mass of microorganisms is localized in the upper soil horizons rich in organic matter. The lower the soil horizon in the soil profile, the the number of microorganisms decreases, and more or less sharply depending on the type of soil. [1]

The number and qualitative composition of microorganisms in the soil also depends on the season. For example, almost in all types of soils, a sharp increase in the physiological activity and number of microorganisms is observed in the season of spring.

The following microorganisms were found in the soils of cereal plants of Absheron:

1. Destructors - bacteria that live in the soil and mineralize basic compounds located in the upper layer of the earth. Their role is transformation remnants of living substances and plants into eclectic elements.

2. Nitrogen-fixing microorganisms (which are divided into associative, symbiotic, free-living) - plant symbionts. Their significance is that only this type of bacteria is capable of combine inorganic oxygen

elements and provide plants with them. It is because of this that the soil and plants receive important minerals.

3. Chemoautotrophs - microorganisms that concentrate existing inorganic substances into basic molecules. Their significance lies in the fact that they can process the eclectic elements that accumulate in the base, and then transfer them to plants. [2]

In the southern latitudes during the season of dry and hot summer the number of microorganisms is sharply reduced, while while in the soils of the northern zone (under conditions of sufficient moisture), fluctuations in the number of microorganisms are less pronounced. On the dynamics of the number of microorganisms in the soil influence not only humidity and temperature, but also the phase of plant development, the entry of organic decay into the soil, the accumulation of microbial metabolites and much more. In addition to seasonal fluctuations in numbers microorganisms, changes in the number and structure of microbial groups are observed in the soil over short periods of time - months, weeks, and even day[4, p.300].

During the research, it was found that in the process of development, plants and microorganisms have learned not only to exist peacefully with each other, but and enter into various symbiotic relationships. Translation nitrogen from the atmosphere to the soil, converting it into a form available to plants. In return, they receive the necessary carbohydrates and mineral salts that plants absorbed from the air. Increasing the level of nitrogen in the soil has a positive effect on plants: they accelerate the development of roots, strengthens immunity, increases resistance stresses and pathogens, and as a result, the amount of yield increases [3].

Many microorganisms secrete antibiotic substances and thereby protect plants from phytopathogens, some are able to synthesize growth stimulants for plants. But at the same time, many bacteria, under certain conditions, are able to carry out the process of denitrification, which leads to nitrogen deficiency in the soil.

Most pathogens of plant diseases actively synthesize hydrolytic enzymes (pectinases, cellulases, proteases, etc.), which cause maceration of plant tissues and destruction of cell membranes, which allows the microbe to penetrate into the plant cell. Being inside the

cell, microorganisms disrupt the normal course of physiological processes, primarily photosynthesis and respiration. Toxins released by pathogens suppress the life-defining enzyme systems of the plant cell, thereby causing its death (picture 1).

Picture 1

If the pathogen is concentrated in the vascular system, the entire plant is affected. Focal or limited lesions are often observed on leaves, trunks, branches, roots and rhizomes.

Plants, in turn, have various protective devices aimed at preventing the penetration of microbes into the body: structural features of integumentary tissues, cell sap reaction, the presence of phytoncides (antibiotic substances), phytoalexins (inhibit the growth of microorganisms in plant tissues), etc.

For fungal diseases, the following symptoms are especially typical:

- the formation of pustules, sporozh, sclerotia, pycnidia, mycelial plaque or layer on individual organs of the plant;

- a change in the color of plant organs in the form of spots or stripes (in the absence of pycnidia, mycelium and other fungal structures, these signs can also appear with non-parasitic, viral, bacterial, fungal diseases, nematode damage);

- discoloration of all aerial parts of the plant, associated with a change in the color of the roots, the base of the stems, conductive bundles (also caused by non-parasitic factors, viruses, bacteria, insects living in plant tissues);

- withering or dying off, associated with a change in the color of the roots or browning of the vessels of the stem (when mucus appears, a possible cause of damage is bacteria);

- dry rots (wet rots appear when affected by bacteria or when a primary infection with fungi and a secondary bacterial infection).

If the cause of the lesion cannot be unequivocally determined by the general.

Fungi infect plants at different stages of development. Many diseases caused by micromycetes are specific to certain age groups of forest plants. For example,

the lodging of seedlings, which is characteristic of the initial phase of plant development, is expressed in the defeat of an immature root collar. During this period, seedlings of forest species are in a herbaceous state and are attacked by fungi.

The soils of forest nurseries located on the sites of former agricultural lands contain a fungus from the genus *Fusarium* - one of the main pathogens of lodging of pine seedlings, especially in the lake basin. Baikal. Many species of the genus *Fusarium* are polyphages, that is, they infect various plants. With prolonged cultivation on the same area of plants susceptible to these fungi, the infection accumulates in the soil. In such nurseries, decay of seedlings is more often observed, caused by micromycete - sclerotinia of cereals. In the asset of this fungus, in addition to seedlings of forest species, cultivated and wild-growing cereals. Damping can also be caused by basidiomycete - typhus of cereals, which affects many cereals. Both pathogens are detected immediately after the snow melts along mycelial films that entangle seedlings with drooping needles. The mycelium of the tiphuli is grayish in color, and the sclerotinia is snow-white. In the development cycle of both pathogens, there are sclerotia, which during the summer fall to the ground from the needles, from the axils of the needles, from the stems and germinate in autumn. Sporulation of these fungi infect plants.

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